

Comparative Examination of the Definition of Assault in the Criminal Code Act, 1916 of Nigeria and The Criminal Code Act, 1889 of Queensland, Australia

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Abstract

Assault is a civil wrong and a criminal offence at law. Hence, it is both a tort and a crime, and an aggrieved person is at liberty to pursue either of the two causes or both. But this paper focuses on the crime. The mens rea is intention to inspire fear of an attack in another or to make the recipient apprehensive of an attack as a present reality, or to have foreseen that that would be the effect on the victim, or to make physical contact with the person, directly or indirectly, without the person's consent, or even with his consent, provided consent was not obtained fraudulently. The actus reus is the unlawful actual physical contact or the larger than life threat of it. Engendered in this definition is battery, which is the actual unlawful physical contact. Hence, the word 'assault' may be used also to cover battery. This paper explores, comparatively, the express twin provisions of Section 252 of the Nigerian Criminal Code Act, 1916 and that of Section 245 of the Queensland Criminal Code Act, 1899 as regards the crime of assault which are exactly the same with the Nigerian Code, having been derived from the Queensland Code, and exceptions to the rules in the said sections of both laws, and from comparative examination of both the letters of the law and the law in motion in the law court, derives a compendium of similarities and differences. This paper further examines the defenses provided in both statutes for the offense of assault which are for the most part the same in both jurisdictions.

1.0 Introduction

Assault is a tort and a crime at law. Its origins can be traced to the Common Law which distinguished between assault and battery as separate offenses. However, modern statutes in Common Law jurisdictions including Nigeria and the Queensland in Australia, lump both offenses together in one statutory definition in Section 252 of the Criminal Code Act, 1916 in Southern Nigeria (NCC) and the Queensland Criminal Code Act, 1899 (Queensland Code). The Nigerian Criminal Code Act was modeled after the Criminal Code drafted by a prominent English Criminal Lawyer, Sir James Fitzstephen, in 1878. This research is conducted with the comparative doctrinal approach with a view to drawing critical inferences in terms of the differences and similarities between the subject codes, and areas of strengths and weaknesses, to derive critical findings on gaps and improvements needed in the Nigerian statute.

2.0 Conceptualization of Key Concepts that Underpin the Crime of Assault

For the purpose of clarity and for proper construction of the context within which the issues the paper addresses are marshaled and treated, it is fundamental to give definitions to key concepts and to understand

the theoretical foundations that underpin the statutory provisions on assault in both the Queensland Criminal Code and the Nigerian Criminal Code. To this end, the following concepts are given contextual definitions from the statutes, and the examined theories set the context of the provisions, as the legal disputes arising from the crime of assault turns on them:

1. Consent; and
2. Bodily Harm/Harm and Grievous Bodily Harm/Grievous Harm.

2.1 Consent

The concept of ‘consent’ underpins the definition of certain offenses against the person such as assault. The presence or absence of consent may avail an accused person of a defense at law or it may not depending on the circumstances. Hence, a lack of consent may transform an otherwise legitimate action into an unlawful one.¹

The doctrine of consent governs inter-personal interactions and sets boundaries for lawful and unlawful conduct among persons, and to protect the integrity of the body.² In general, consent is not a determinant factor in ascribing liability for the crime of murder and abortion. However, consent may absolve an accused of liability in some crimes, in recognition of the personal liberty of persons.³

Stemming from the legal recognition of the liberty of persons is the right to bodily integrity and safety from harm, which facts underscore society’s notion of safety.

The Nigerian Criminal Code does not define ‘consent’. The Queensland Code⁴ defines consent in relation to the offense of assault in Section 352 in the following terms:

- (1) In this chapter, *consent* means consent freely and voluntarily given by a person with the cognitive capacity to give the consent.
- (2) Without limiting subsection (1), a person’s consent to an act is not freely and voluntarily given if it is obtained—
 - (a) by force; or
 - (b) by threat or intimidation; or
 - (c) by fear of bodily harm; or
 - (d) by exercise of authority; or
 - (e) by false and fraudulent representations about the nature or purpose of the act; or
 - (f) by a mistaken belief induced by the accused person that the accused person was the person’s sexual partner.

¹ Miriam Gur-Aye, ‘Consent in Criminal Law’ (Edgar Encyclopedia of Comparative Law, 2020) 379.

² KL Koh, ‘The Doctrine of Consent in Criminal Law’ (Malaya Law Review, 1967) (9) 181.

³ Ibid.

⁴ S 348, Criminal Code Act, 1899, Queensland.

Historically, consent was not a defense to criminal offenses as such offenses were of a public nature, hence they were within the purview of the state to prosecute, and not the individual so offended. That much can be gleaned from the decision of the English Court in *R v Coney (1881)*.⁵ It only applied to the Tort or civil wrong.⁶ But, in the modern context, consent is critical to criminal assault.⁷

However, consent is not required for everyday inevitable physical contacts not arising willfully, but out of necessity. Consent may be tacit or implied⁸. Thus, if one loses one's belonging in traffic and another who sees it and picks it up and tries to draw one's attention to return it by a slight touch, though that touch is not done with one's consent, it does not amount to assault.⁹ If in trying to pass through a narrow tunnel, a man comes in close physical contact with another, though without the consent of the other, it would not be assault. Similarly, in contact sports like football and wrestling, contact between opponents, though without the consent of the other party does not amount to assault,¹⁰ except it was done with malicious intent.

Consent is irrelevant in those cases where the state is duty-bound to protect the weak and helpless. Hence, in offenses like homicide and having carnal knowledge of an underage person, consent is irrelevant. In general, consent is not an excuse for prohibited conduct. Although some of the reasons for exceptions to criminal liability for certain offenses for which consent is a part of their definitions are now untraceable, they have become part of modern criminal law. Hence, although assault is criminal, exceptions for accidental and inevitable physical contacts not done maliciously, and which arise from everyday interactions with other human beings and while commuting, are exempted.¹¹

Yet, there are instances a person may consent to some violence to be done to his body for medical purposes such as surgery, and the law permits that.¹² Yet, when a patient who is competent withholds consent to a medical procedure, the medical doctor who proceeds to administer such procedure would be guilty of assault. Hence, in a Canadian case,¹³ consent must be freely given. Under the Law of Informed Consent which topic is beyond the purview of this paper, applicable to doctor-patient relationship, the patient's consent to a procedure must stem from his understanding of the procedure from clear and unambiguous information given to him by the doctor. Where it was obtained by hazy information or deceit, it amounts to assault as the doctor lacks real consent.

⁵ (1882) 8 QBD 534.

⁶ *ibid.*

⁷ *R v Bonora (1987) WAR 280.*

⁸ *Horan v Ferguson (1994) CA 85/1994 35.*

⁹ CO Okonkwo, *Criminal Law in Nigeria (Spectrum Books Limited, 2018) 285.*

¹⁰ *Ibid*; *Simms vs Leigh Rugby Football Club (1969) 2 All ER 923.*

¹¹ KM Harrison, *Law, Order, and the Consent Defense (St. Louis U. Pub, 1993) 479-480.*

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ *Beausoleil v Sisters of Charity (1964) 53 DLR 65.*

Although it has been established that where consent is obtained by fraud or deceit, the accused remains liable for assault, this needs some further clarification as this may not always be so in some circumstances. Assault may not have occurred where a man lured a full-grown woman into a sexual session by lying he was not a married man, even though consent was fraudulently obtained by a lie.¹⁴

2.2 Bodily Harm/Harm and Grievous Bodily Harm/Grievous Harm

The concept of 'harm' is germane to the definition of crime and punishment in every legal jurisdiction. Albin (1965) opines that the concept of harm may well be useful in the measurement of punishment.¹⁵ Hence, in the crime of assault, the offence might be classified as a misdemeanour or a felony, depending on the gravity of the harm inflicted on the victim, and that as a consequence helps determine the gravity of punishment inflicted by the Court on the accused.

Assault may result in some discomfort or irritation or some health dysfunction or some disability to one to whom some tactile force is applied or one who apprehends some hurt due to the action or conduct of an accused. Assault may be classified depending on whether or not some degree of harm is inflicted on the victim in the course of the assault. The law is inclined to visit commensurate punishment for assault of any kind. This is the *raison d'être* for espousing the concepts of harm or bodily harm and grievous bodily harm and grievous harm within the context of the Criminal Code Act of Southern Nigerian and the Criminal Code Act of Queensland, Australia, as this forms the basis of the classification into common assault where no harm or bodily injury results from assault, assault occasioning bodily harm or grievous bodily harm, and assault occasioning harm or bodily harm. Apart from the foregoing classifications, there is also serious assaults related to unlawful interventions in preventing the arrest of a suspect or to resist detention, or to prevent a person authorized by law or a police officer from carrying out their lawful tasks or or in pursuance of a conspiracy in respect of any manufacture, trade, business, or occupation, or in respect of anyone concerned in the manufacture, trade, business, or occupation, or the wages of any person, in respect of the assault of persons who are 60 years or above, or a disabled person.¹⁶

The Criminal Code of Southern Nigeria¹⁷ defines harm as "bodily hurt, disease, or disorder, whether permanent or temporary". The Queensland Code¹⁸ uses the term 'bodily harm' which it defines as 'any bodily injury which interferes with health or comfort.' 'bodily harm' in the Queensland Code carries the same import as 'harm' carries in the NCC.

¹⁴ CO Okonkwo (supra); R v Clarence (1888) QBD 23 at 43 per Stephen J.

¹⁵ Albin Eser, 'The Principle of Harm in the Concept of Crime: A Comparative Analysis of the Criminally Protected Legal Interests' (Duquesne Law Review, 1965) (4) 346.

¹⁶ Section 340 of the Queensland Code.

¹⁷ Section 1 (Interpretation Section) of the NCC, .

¹⁸ Section 1 (Interpretation Section) of the Queensland Code.

Section 1 of the NCC further distinguishes ‘harm’ from ‘grievous harm’, reflecting a higher magnitude of harm in the following terms:

“Grievous harm means any harm which amounts to a maim or dangerous harm as defined in this section, or which seriously or permanently injures health, or which is likely to injure health, or which extends to permanent disfigurement or to any permanent or serious injury to any external or internal organ, member, or sense.”

The Queensland Code uses the term ‘grievous bodily harm’ instead, and defines it as follows:

“grievous bodily harm means—

- (a) the loss of a distinct part or an organ of the body; or
- (b) serious disfigurement; or
- (c) any bodily injury of such a nature that, if left untreated, would endanger or be likely to endanger life, or cause or be likely to cause permanent injury to health; whether or not treatment is or could have been available.

Consequently, ‘harm’ in the NCC means the same thing as ‘bodily harm’ in the Queensland Code and ‘grievous harm’ and ‘grievous bodily harm’, for all intents and purposes, carry the same meaning in both codes respectively.

Having set the context for proper construction of the crime of assault, the focus now shifts to the detailed examination of the crime of assault.

3.0 Comparative Analysis of the Elements of Criminal Assault in the Queensland Code and the NCC

Criminal assault is assault defined by law as a crime. A good starting point in examining the crime of assault is to consider the exact statutory provisions in respect of assault in the relevant laws, to wit: the Queensland Code and the NCC.

The Queensland Code defines the crime of assault in Section 245 thus:

(1) A person who strikes, touches, or moves, or otherwise applies force of any kind to, the person of another, either directly or indirectly, without the other person’s consent, or with the other person’s consent if the consent is obtained by fraud, or who by any bodily act or gesture attempts or threatens

to apply force of any kind to the person of another without the other person's consent, under such circumstances that the person making the attempt or threat has actually or apparently a present ability to effect the person's purpose, is said to assault that other person, and the act is called an assault.

(2) In this section— applies force includes the case of applying heat, light, electrical force, gas, odour, or any other substance or thing whatever if applied in such a degree as to cause injury or personal discomfort.

Section 252 of the NCC has the exact same provisions as Section 245 of the Queensland Code .

An examination of the above definition of assault in both codes would yield two ways by which the crime of assault may be committed, to wit:

1. By application of tactile force to the body of a person (referred to in Queensland as Type 1 Assault in Queensland, Australia); and
2. By a threat to apply force such that the person to whom the threat is made apprehends that force would be applied against his body (also called Type 2 Assault in Queensland, Australia).

The first plank of the definition is battery at Common Law while the second plank is assault proper at Common Law.¹⁹ In some instances, both types of assault may be committed all at once as one who was hurt by the application of force by another also apprehended that force would be applied.²⁰ Hence, assault may be seen as inchoate battery or an attempt to commit battery. Battery may be seen as completed assault.²¹ As a matter of fact, at one time, assault was considered an attempt to commit battery.²² However, the Queensland Code and the NCC, in keeping with the modern trend in several other jurisdictions, do not use different terms to describe them, but simply consider both as assault. Hence, it is common to use the term 'assault' in reference to both situations.²³

The second plank of the definition of assault in both the codes further require that threat or attempt apprehended by the victim should be such that he also apprehends that '... the person making the attempt or threat has actually or apparently a present ability to effect the person's purpose ...'. In essence, the victim must be apprehensive of an immediate harm as a result of the accused attempting or threatening to apply

¹⁹ Graham McBain, 'Modernizing the Common Law Offenses of Assault and Battery' (International Law Research, 2015) (4) 39; *Collins v Willcock* (1984) 1 WLR 1172.

²⁰ Yash Rupeshkumar, 'Critical Analysis of Assault and Battery' (International Journal of Law Management & Humanities, 2023) (6) 760.

²¹ Uduak Ikono, 'Determining the Actus Reus of Attempt: Legal Issues and Options' (International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, 2019) (3) 6.

²² Rollins Perkins, 'An Analysis of Assault and Attempts to Assault' (Minnesota Law Review, 1962) 71.

²³ Yash Rupeshkumar (supra).

some force upon his person. Okonkwo (*supra*) opines that though the definition of assault in the code is silent about the victim's state of mind, the Court is more likely to lean towards an objective test (the reasonable man's test).²⁴

Both the second paragraph of Section 252 of the NCC and Section 245(2) of the Queensland Code further qualify the first plank of the definition of assault by giving clarity to the application of force by the suspect and the degree to which it is applied for the act to constitute assault. It is common assault to merely apply force but with no harm done. It is also common assault to create in the mind of the victim an apprehension of immediate harm even though no harm was done. To constitute an assault causing harm or bodily harm or grievous harm or grievous bodily harm or serious assault, the force must have been applied to such degree as to cause varying degrees of harm or bodily harm or grievous bodily harm and grievous harm in both codes to the victim. The sources of such force may include heat, light, electrical force, gas, odour, or like things capable of causing varying degrees of harm or personal discomfort when applied. Hence, to puff exhaled smoke from cigarette in the face of another person or to break wind or fart in the presence of another may constitute an assault if it is done to such extent as to cause discomfort for the person.²⁵

But, merely uttering words of threat without more is not sufficient to convict an accused person for assault, except they are accompanied by some overt bodily act or gesture.²⁶ Again, if in the circumstance in which the accused acted like he would draw a weapon while making a statement that negatives intent, there is no assault.²⁷

The definition of assault in the first plank shows that the force applied may be direct or indirect. The question of direct application of force is in respect of the first plank and it is self-explanatory. However, the question of indirect application of force needs further clarification from case law. In *R v Martin (1881)*²⁸ D placed an iron bar in an escape route and put out the lights in a theatre filled to capacity and the spectators panicked and scampered out in fear and in the process, some of the spectators got injured. D was convicted of inflicting grievous bodily harm. On appeal, the Court held that he was rightly convicted and his appeal was dismissed. Similarly, in *R v Halliday (1889)*²⁹ the defendant's wife jumped through the window on the first floor to escape violent attacks from him and she broke a leg. He was convicted for willfully and maliciously causing bodily harm and assault occasioning actual bodily harm, even though he did not directly throw her out of the window.

²⁴ CO Okonkwo (*supra*) 272.

²⁵ CO Okonkwo (*supra*) 283.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ *Tuberville v Savage* (1669) 1 Mod. Rep 3.

²⁸ *R v Martin* (1881) 8 QBD 54

²⁹ *R v Halliday* (1889) 61 LT 701.

Both codes envisage that the attempt or threat of force by some bodily act or gesture would be immediate, hence the the words ‘... in such circumstances that the person making the attempt or threat has actually or apparently a present ability’ used in the codes in qualifying the second plank of the definition. Hence, If one person points a loaded or unloaded gun at another, that would amount to assault as there is clearly an immediate capacity to effect the purpose.³⁰ It would seem that if a person formed a gun with his fingers and points it at another, that would not be assault, as there is no actual or apparent capacity to effect the purpose.

The definition of the second plank suggests that the threat or attempt must be contemporaneous with the apprehension of fear and the actual or apparent capacity to inflict harm. Hence, I submit, it would also seem that where B knows A to be a criminal or a cultist and A forms a gun with his finger and points it at B, it would also not be assault, though it inspires fear in B that A plans to harm him with a gun as we see in the movies, though it satisfies the requirement of an attempt or threat, but there is no actual or apparent capacity to effect the purpose. Usually, in the movies, when a criminal points his fingers in form of a gun at another or he slides his forefinger across his throat, it is a sign of a death threat. This bears all the elements of the crime threatening violence instead in Section 75 or Section 359 of the Queensland Code, depending on who is so threatened. In Nigeria, it would fall under Section 86 (threatening violence) or Section 327 (threats to kill) or Sections 392-409 (threats in relation to property and extortion), depending on the circumstances of the case.

One of the underpinning factors in the definition of the crime of assault as identified earlier in this paper is the lack of consent or consent obtained by fraud. The above statutory definition of assault shows that the crime is committed when the threat or tactile bodily contact is done without the permission of the victim or where such permission or consent was obtained by fraud or deceit. Save for allowances the law makes in recognition of the necessity for physical contacts in everyday interactions, leisurely activities including sports and commuting earlier identified in this paper, all assaults are unlawful without competent consent, except otherwise specified by law. In essence, assault may be lawful or unlawful.

Thus, in sporting activities, some allowance is made for assault and consent is assumed. But where, in sporting activities, a footballer, for example, goes for the jaws of his opponent to break it in the course of a match may be guilty of assault causing bodily harm as no rules of sport can make lawful what the criminal law deems unlawful.³¹

3.1 Lawful and Unlawful Assaults

Section 253 of the NCC and Section 246 of the Queensland Code both define unlawful assaults in exactly the same terms as follows:

³⁰ CO Okonkwo (supra) 282.

³¹ R Wood, J Biggs & K Murray, Legal Studies for Queensland (2025) Chap 30.

An assault is unlawful and constitutes an offence unless it is authorised or justified or excused by law.

The application of force by one person to the person of another may be unlawful, although it is done with the consent of that other person.

From the wordings of the above provisions in both codes, every assault is unlawful except as otherwise allowed by the codes. Hence, the codes provide circumstances under which certain actions that would ordinarily have constituted assault would not amount to the crime. Assault may be lawful or justified when the code says so. Some reasonable level of force, where no wound is inflicted on the subject or does not cause harm to him may be justified for the purpose of chastising a child under 16 by a parent or one in loco parentis for disobedience.³² Similarly, a master training a person or a house owner may also apply some force not amounting to harm upon his house help for the purpose of correction commits no assault. It is also lawful assault when reasonable force commensurate with the threat is applied in self defense, in the execution of the sentence of a court³³, in the execution of a warrant³⁴, to prevent a crime suspect from escaping arrest³⁵, to prevent a breach of the peace,³⁶ to suppress a riot,³⁷ in defence of a place of dwelling,³⁸ on provocation,³⁹ in defence of moveable property⁴⁰, for the preservation of order aboard a ship,⁴¹ and for surgical operations,⁴² subject, however, to the limit that the force is not excessive or incommensurate with the force of resistance or threat which the person to whom it is applied to lawfully presents or poses.⁴³

Where assault is as a result of the consent of the victim, it may yet be unlawful. Thus, a consent by a person to the causing of his death is inexcusable in both codes and the person by whom it is caused is not absolved of criminal responsibility.⁴⁴ An infant at law or an invalid or person labouring under a severe infirmity of the mind or suffering from a mental problem is incapable of granting consent. Similarly, consent obtained under threat or by force amounts to no consent.⁴⁵ Consent is also ineffectual if the assault is of a nature as to endanger human life or to cause a breach of the peace. Hence in *Matthews v Ollerton*,⁴⁶ it was held that the “licence to beat me is void, because ‘tis against the breach of the peace.”

³²R Wood, J Biggs & K Murray (supra) 284.

³³ Section 254 NCC (supra).

³⁴ Ibid, Section 256.

³⁵ Ibid, Section 271.

³⁶ Ibid, Section 275.

³⁷ Ibid, Section 276.

³⁸ Ibid, Section 282.

³⁹ Ibid, Section 283.

⁴⁰ Ibid, Section 289.

⁴¹ Ibid, Section 296.

⁴² Ibid, Section 297.

⁴³ Ibid, Section 298..

⁴⁴ Ibid, Section 299.

⁴⁵ CO Okonkwo (supra) 285.

⁴⁶ *Matthews v Ollerton* (1692) Comb 218.

The crime of assault permeates the definition of every crime entailing violence in both codes. Hence, it is one of the elements of rape, sexual assault, murder, manslaughter and a host of other crimes.

3.2 Mens Rea and Actus Reus of Assault

The act or attempt in the crime of assault must be done in a particular mental state. The mental state is intention to do harm or to cause an apprehension of harm would be done by the accused in the victim. Assault must be intentional⁴⁷ Inchoate assault is punished by the law with the view to preventing the commission of crime or to prevent the doing of any act that is harmful to society or to a person.

In Nigeria, intention is an element of the crime of assault in both the first plank and the second plank of its definition in Section 252 of the NCC.⁴⁸ Thus in *Okekearu v Tanko (2002)*,⁴⁹ The Supreme Court held that battery (the first plank of the definition of assault in Section 252) requires that the act be done intentionally or negligently. That intention is an element in assault described in the first plank of Section 252 is further corroborated by the decision of the Court of Appeal in *Adamu v IGP & Ors (2013)*.⁵⁰

Also in *Ndibe v Ndibe (1998)*⁵¹ the Court of Appeal, in reference to the second plank of the definition of assault in Section 252 of the NCC, opined that assault is an intentional act that causes another to apprehend immediate unlawful force.

However, the exact position of the law of assault on intention in the first plank of the definition of assault in Section 245 of the Queensland Code is contentious and hazy as there have been conflicting judgments among Courts in Queensland and Western Australia which has the same wordings in Section 222 of the Criminal Code Act Compilation Act, 1913 for the same offence as those of the Queensland Code's Section 245. It is settled law in Queensland as in Nigeria that intention is an element in an attempt or threat of harm engendered in the second plank of the definition of assault. In Queensland also, intention is an element in the definition of assault in the first plank just as in Nigeria. Hence, in a Queensland case, *Issitt v Commissioner of Police (2016)*,⁵² the Queensland District Court held that intention was an element in the crime of assault defined in the first plank of the definition where force is applied. Although this position is hotly contested by legal luminaries in Queensland including Duffy (2024)⁵³ who considers the decision as inappropriate and believes that the position of the Court of Appeal in Western Australia in respect of the same subject in

⁴⁷ Smith v. State, 39 Miss. 521, 525 (1860);

⁴⁸ CO Okonkwo 282 (supra).

⁴⁹ Okekearu v Tanko (2002) 15 NWLR (Pt 791) 657.

⁵⁰ Adamu v IGP & Ors (2013) LPELR-22812 (CA).

⁵¹ Ndibe v Ndibe (1998) 5 NWLR (Pt 551) 632.

⁵² Issitt v Commissioner of Police (Qld) (2016) QDC 308.

⁵³ James Duffy, Assault and the Mental Element of Intention in the Queensland Criminal Code (Criminal Law Journal, 2024) 47(2).

Section 222 of the Criminal Code Act Compilation Act, 1913 in *Hayman v Cartwright (2018)*⁵⁴ to the effect that intention is not an element of the offence of assault defined on the first plank of the definition in the code. A discussion of the contention is beyond the purview of this paper.

The crime of assault may not be committed by omission. Hence, in *Fagan v MPC (1969)*⁵⁵ the Court dismissed the claim of an appellant who had been convicted for assault by the lower Court to the effect that he had no intention to commit assault as he had not deliberately driven his car upon the foot of the police officer and kept it there, claiming it was an omission, and assault could not be committed by omission. The Court ruled that though the appellant had not formed the mens rea for assault when he drove his car on the foot of the officer and kept it there, but the fact that he kept it on the officer's foot after he had been told to move it off and he had hesitated for while amounts to a continuing act during which the mens rea was formed. Hence James J ruled at page 445 of the judgment: **“It is not necessary that mens rea should be present at the inception of the actus reus; it can be superimposed upon an existing act.”** Section 23(2) of the Queensland Code further clarifies the fact that omission is not an element of assault as it is not part of the definition of the offense, to wit:

(2) Unless the intention to cause a particular result is expressly declared to be an element of the offence constituted, in whole or part, by an act or omission, the result intended to be caused by an act or omission is immaterial.

The office of the Attorney-General of Australia provides definitions of intention in respect to the Criminal Code as consisting of intention in relation to conduct, in relation to a circumstance, and in respect to a result.⁵⁶ A person manifests intention in relation to conduct if he means to engage in the conduct. When it comes to a circumstance, a person's intention becomes manifest if he so believes that it exists or will exist. In relation to a result, intention is manifest if the person means to bring it about or is aware that it will occur in the ordinary course of events.

The actus reus is the act or gesture of the suspect that causes the victim to be apprehensive of an immediate actual or apparent threat of harm to his person or that causes harm in varying degrees to the victim. Assault could be a continuing act.⁵⁷ Any amount of force, even a slight touch could constitute the actus reus of assault.⁵⁸ A person's clothing is an extension of the person. Touching it may constitute assault.⁵⁹ Where

⁵⁴ *Hayman v Cartwright (2018)* 53 WAR 137 (81)-(85) A Crim R 439; (2018) WASCA 116.

⁵⁵ 1 QB 439.

⁵⁶ Attorney-General's Department, '5.2 Intention' (Australian Government) <
<https://www.ag.gov.au/crime/publications/commonwealth-criminal-code-guide-practitioners-draft/part-22-elements-offence/division-5-fault-elements/52-intention> > Accessed 5 October, 2025.

⁵⁷ *Fagan v Commissioner of Metropolitan Police (1969)* 1 QB 439.

⁵⁸ *DPP v JWH (2000)* NSWSC.

⁵⁹ *R v Day (2004)* NSWCCA.

assault entails attempt or a threat, the victim must be aware of the act.⁶⁰ Consent is also a critical *actus reus*.⁶¹

The state of the mind of the victim of assault does not have to be one of fear. It suffices that he is apprehensive that harm would be done to him. Hence, in *Brady v Schatzel (1911)*⁶² though A pointed a loaded gun at B, threatening to shoot him, and B testified in Court that he entertained no fear, it was held that it amounted to assault.

3.4 Punishment for Assault

As established earlier, the degree of harm occasioned by an assault determines the magnitude of the punishment imposed by criminal law on the accused. It goes to weight in meting out appropriate punishment as prescribed by law. The legal consequences spelt out by law based on the gravity of harm caused by an assault is the distinguishing factor between common assaults and aggravated forms of assault and serious assault.

Common assault attracts 3 years imprisonment in Queensland, making it a felony.⁶³ In Nigeria, common assault is a misdemeanour attracting 1 year imprisonment.⁶⁴

The Queensland Code and the NCC differ on the punishment for occasioning grievous harm or grievous bodily harm though both codes make it a felony. Section 335 of the NCC makes a person who commits assault occasioning grievous harm liable to 7 years imprisonment. As earlier mentioned, the equivalent of grievous harm in the NCC in the Queensland Code is grievous bodily harm. Section 320(1)-(4) of the Queensland Code imposes 14 years imprisonment for the same offense, but further qualifies the punishment in respect of an offender who belongs to a criminal organization and does grievous bodily harm to a police officer in the course of executing his duty, committing him to a mandatory 1 year jail sentence without parole.

In Queensland, assault occasioning bodily harm attracts 7 years imprisonment when done alone and without a dangerous or offensive weapon, and 10 years imprisonment when done with a dangerous or offensive weapon or in the company of one or more other persons.⁶⁵ In Nigeria, it attracts 7 years imprisonment.⁶⁶

⁶⁰ R v Pemble (1971) 124 CLR 107 (HCA).

⁶¹ R v Bonora (supra).

⁶² Brady v Schatzel (1911) ST R Qd 206.

⁶³ Section 335 Queensland Code.

⁶⁴ Section 351 NCC.

⁶⁵ Section 339 Queensland Code (supra);

⁶⁶ Section 335 NCC (supra).

In Nigeria, serious assault is a felony and consists of assaults done under aggravating circumstances, hence the term aggravated assault. Such assaults may occur in the defendant's bid to commit a felony, assault with weapons, assault of a public officer to prevent him from carrying out his lawful duty or to prevent anyone performing a lawful duty etc.⁶⁷ In Queensland, serious assaults consist of the same set of actions spelled out under the NCC but adds assault against one who is 60 years and above and assaults against the disabled or physically challenged person.⁶⁸

In Nigeria, indecent assault on females attracts 2 years imprisonment.⁶⁹ For indecent assault on males, the punishment is 3 years imprisonment.⁷⁰ The Queensland Code makes general provisions for sexual assaults.

To guard against the activities of pirates at sea, assault against one protecting a ship caught in a shipwreck is a felony and attracts 7 years imprisonment.⁷¹

Although, the NCC is silent on assaults committed in interference with the freedom of trade or work, the Queensland Code makes provision for 5 years imprisonment as punishment.⁷²

In Nigeria, assault with intent to commit unnatural offence like sodomy or homosexuality attracts 14 years imprisonment.⁷³ In the Queensland Code, there is no such provision.

In the Queensland Code, sexual assaults attracts a maximum of 10 years imprisonment generally.⁷⁴ However, where a person is assaulted under Section 352(1)(a) and Section 352(1)(b)(i) where the indecent assault or act of gross indecency includes bringing into contact any part of the genitalia or the anus of a person with any part of the mouth of a person, the penalty is a maximum of 14 years. Where the offender is armed or pretends to be armed with a dangerous or offensive weapon or is in the company of another person before, during and immediately after the offence, or where under Section 352(1)(a), the offender penetrated the victim's vagina, vulva or anus with any object other than the penis, or where under Section 352(1)(b)(i) the offender procures another person to penetrate the vagina, vulva or anus of the victim or of the person who is procured with an object other than the penis, the penalty is life imprisonment. The NCC has no such provisions, except for provisions related to rape, indecent assaults and the like.

⁶⁷ Section 356 NCC.

⁶⁸ Section 340 Queensland Code (supra).

⁶⁹ Ibid, Section 360.

⁷⁰ Ibid, Section 353.

⁷¹ Ibid, Section 354.

⁷² Section 346 Queensland Code.

⁷³ Ibid, Section 352.

⁷⁴ Section 352 Queensland Code.

For assault with intent to commit rape in the Queensland Code,⁷⁵ the penalty is 14 years imprisonment.

4.0 Defenses for Assault

The defenses for assault in both the Queensland Code (Sections 247-282) and the NCC (Sections 254 - 297) are the same. One who stands trial for assault has recourse to the following defenses:

1. **Consent:** Consent generally vitiates criminal liability for assault under certain circumstances, provided it does not result in harm to the victim. Where it results in bodily or grievous bodily harm, the offender is criminally liable for assault and may be committed to prison in line with the prescriptions of the law earlier discussed in this paper. Consent is no excuse for an assault resulting in the death of the victim,⁷⁶ except where the law so provides.
2. **Intention:** The intention of the offender may serve to vitiate criminal liability for assault in both jurisdictions, except where death is a result.⁷⁷
3. **Exercise of lawful authority:** Hence when one exercises lawful authority in effecting an arrest, executing a sentence of a court, executing a warrant, executing a court process, prevention of escape from arrest etc, assaults are lawful to the extent allowable by the law, provided the infliction of grievous bodily harm does not occur.
4. **Preventing a breach of the public peace:** Both codes permit the use of reasonable force commensurate to the danger preventing a breach of peace or its continuance or its renewal.⁷⁸
5. **Suppression of riots:** An accused in both jurisdictions may also rely on Sections 276-280 (NCC) and Sections 261-265 (Queensland Code) respectively depending on the circumstances when force is used to quell a riot.
6. **Prevention of Offenses Crimes and Offenses for which an offender may be arrested without warrant:** Both the NCC and the Queensland Code made provision for the use of force by any person for the prevention of the commission of crime, or to prevent any act from being done on reasonable grounds would amount to an offense when carried out, or to prevent one

⁷⁵ Section 351 Queensland Code.

⁷⁶ Section 299 NCC; Section 284 Queensland Code.

⁷⁷ Section 299 NCC; Section 284 Queensland Code; *Ndibe v Ndibe* (1998) 5 NWLR (Pt 551) 632;⁷⁷ *Issit v Commissioner of Police (Qld)* (2016) QDC 308.

⁷⁸ Section 275 NCC; Section 260 Queensland Code.

who the offender reasonably believes is under some infirmity of the mind or an invalid from doing violence to another person or property.⁷⁹

7. **In the Defence of a Dwelling House:** Where the owner of a property or one who lawfully occupies it or any person assisting him believes on reasonable grounds the other person is trying to enter or to remain in the dwelling with intent to commit an indictable offense, he is allowed to use force to repel or prevent the unlawful party from gaining access or remaining in the property.⁸⁰
8. **Provocation:** Both codes allow for a defense of provocation when an assault is an element, including any act that amounts to an insult as would likely when done to an ordinary person, or in the presence of an ordinary person under the care of the person so insulted, or to one's spouse, child, sibling, parent, or friend, or to one's boss or employee, or would elicit a loss of self-control and induce an assault in reaction. This also applies when assault occurs in a bid to prevent the repetition of an insult.⁸¹
9. **In Self-Defense and in the defense of property:** The use of reasonable force commensurate with the threat is also permissible in the defense of oneself during an attack and in the defense of one's property as well as the right to access an easement.⁸²
10. **For the administration of domestic discipline:** Both codes also make provisions for the application of force reasonable under the circumstances by parents or persons in loco parentis for the correction, discipline, management and control of a child or pupil under their care.⁸³
11. **Preservation of order on a vessel or vehicle:** In both codes, the captain of a ship or an aircraft is permitted to use reasonable force against anyone onboard with a view to suppressing any mutiny, hijack or disorder in order to protect the vehicle; he is also permitted to kill any person who is guilty or or aids and abets such disorder, if the safety of the vehicle or of passengers or any other persons onboard cannot be guaranteed otherwise.⁸⁴
12. **For Surgical Procedures and Palliative Medical Care:** Both the NC and the Queensland Code provide for the use of force reasonable for the performance of surgical procedures by

⁷⁹ Section 281 NCC; Section 266 Queensland Code.

⁸⁰ Section 282 NCC; Section 267 Queensland Code.

⁸¹ Sections 283-287 NCC; Sections 268-272 Queensland Code.

⁸² Sections 286-294 NCC; Sections 271-279 Queensland Code.

⁸³ Section 295 NCC; Section 280 Queensland Code.

⁸⁴ Section 296 NCC; Section; Section 281 Queensland Code.

medical professionals and the provision of emergency or first aid care by non-medical professionals or medical professionals to a patient, provided such force is lawful and done with the observance of sound medical standards or direction, and in the administration of medicines, preliminary medical procedures and treatment.⁸⁵

5.0 Findings and Recommendations

In the course of conducting this research, some critical issues came to the fore, to wit:

1. The NCC currently lacks a definitive section for sexual assaults, save for scanty provisions prohibiting indecent assaults against male and female persons, and for homosexuality; sexual assault is a grievous offense against the person which may have life-threatening and life-long consequences upon the victim, male or female; the provision for indecent assaults is not sufficient deterrent or punitive measure neither does it define the related offenses with such clarity as the depth of the provisions of the Queensland Code on sexual assaults;
2. It would seem would seem like the provisions in the NCC on indecent assaults was done with gender bias against female persons who are more vulnerable as the provisions impose higher sentence of 3 years for indecent assault against males compared to 2 years for females; this anomaly needs to be rectified through legislative amendments; and
3. The NCC lacks an equivalent section to Section 282A of the Queensland Code on the administration of palliative care. This is of utmost importance to administration of emergency care and first aid to accident victims and victims of trauma by non-medical professionals to stem the tide of rampant death due to lack of adequate care and intervention before the victim gets to the hospital. Such oversight on the part of the Nigerian legislature is inexcusable. There is need to have this rectified through legislative action.

6.0 Conclusion

The provision of the Section 252 of the NCC and Section 245 of the Queensland Code define the elements of criminal assault. Though they do not distinguish between assault and battery in line with the definition at Common Law from which the provisions are derived, they still distinguish between the two types of assault in the two planks of the definitions. The application of force by an offender with the consent of the victim,

⁸⁵ Section 297 NCC; Sections; Sections 282 & 282A Queensland Code.

or with consent where it was obtained by fraud, forms the core of the definition in the first plank Assault in the second plank turns on the gesture or an attempt of the offender such that it elicits an apprehension of harm or fear that immediate harm would be done to him in the victim by the action of the offender. Both intention and consent may serve to vitiate criminal responsibility in both jurisdictions.

List of Statutes

1. The Nigerian Criminal Code Act, 1916
2. The Criminal Code Act, 1899 (Queensland)
3. The Criminal Code Act Compilation Act, 1913 (Western Australia)

List of Cases

R v Bonora (1987) WAR 280.

R v Coney (1881) (1882) 8 QBD 534.

Horan v Ferguson (1994) CA 85/1994 35.

Simms vs Leigh Rugby Football Club (1969) 2 All ER 923.

Beausoleil v Sisters of Charity (1964) 53 DLR 65.

R v Clarence (1888) QBD 23 at 43 per Stephen J.

Tuberville v Savage (1669) 1 Mod. Rep 3.

R v Martin (1881) 8 QBD 54.

R v Halliday (1889) 61 LT 701.

Matthews v Ollerton (1692) Comb 218.

Smith v. State, 39 Miss. 521, 525 (1860);

Okekearu v Tanko (2002) 15 NWLR (Pt 791) 657.

Adamu v IGP & Ors (2013) LPELR-22812 (CA).

Ndibe v Ndibe (1998) 5 NWLR (Pt 551) 632.

Issit v Commissioner of Police (Qld) (2016) QDC 308.

Fagan v MPC (1969) 1 QB 439.

Hayman v Cartwright (2018) 53 WAR 137 (81)-(85) A Crim R 439; (2018) WASCA 116.

Fagan v Commissioner of Metropolitan Police (1969) 1 QB 439.

DPP v JWH (2000) NSWSC.

R v Day (2004) NSWCCA.

R v Pemble (1971) 124 CLR 107 (HCA).

Brady v Schatzel (1911) ST R Qd 206.

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9. Rollins Perkins, 'An Analysis of Assault and Attempts to Assault' (Minnesota Law Review, 1962) 71.
10. Uduak Ikono, 'Determining the Actus Reus of Attempt: Legal Issues and Options' (International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, 2019) (3) 6.
11. Yash Rupeshkumar, 'Critical Analysis of Assault and Battery' (International Journal of Law Management & Humanities, 2023) (6) 760.